

Local Government in Canada

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Martin Horak

Department of Political Science
Western University

Partners

Eurac Research
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Canada

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Western University: Martin Horak
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Canada: An Introduction

Martin Horak and Brittany VanDenBrink, *Department of Political Science, Western University*

Local Government Revenues

The structure of local financial arrangements in Canada falls largely under provincial control. Provincial governments pass laws that authorize specific ways that municipalities can generate what are called ‘own-source’ revenues. The permissible range of own-source revenues is rather restricted in comparison with many other countries. Own-source revenues are generally limited to local property taxes, user fees charged for services (such as parking, recreation facilities, and tags for garbage collection), and fees charged to property developers. Municipalities are generally not allowed to collect income or sales taxes. At the same time, the fiscal system is highly decentralized – own-source revenues account for more than 75 per cent of all local government revenues in all provinces, and more than 90 per cent of all local government revenues in some provinces, such as British Columbia.⁴⁸

Intergovernmental transfers, which range from about 8 per cent to about 25 per cent of local government revenues depending on the province, fall into one of two categories: unconditional, meaning that the funding can be used at the discretion of the municipality, and conditional, which requires the municipality to use the funding for a specific purpose. The vast majority of intergovernmental transfers come from provincial governments. In Ontario, they are used primarily to help pay for the cost of social services and public health; elsewhere in the country, the provinces are responsible for providing these services. From the federal government, the gas tax is the only significant source of revenue that is transferred to municipalities. The gas tax has been a guaranteed source of municipal revenue since 2013 that is used for subsidizing capital infrastructure projects (thus it is a form of conditional funding). Transfer amounts are determined based on each province’s population, and subsequent distribution is administered by the provinces.⁴⁹

The limited range of local revenue sources, combined with high local fiscal autonomy, means that Canadian local governments are extraordinarily dependent on local property taxes – more so than local governments in any other industrialized country, including the United States. Property taxes account for a majority of own-source local revenues across Canada and constitute a majority of *all* local revenues in several provinces.

In theory, the provinces could grant municipalities the same taxing authority as the provinces have themselves. This means that local income taxes and sales taxes could be levied (as has

⁴⁸ Andrew Sancton, *Canadian Local Government: An Urban Perspective* (2nd edn, OUP 2015) 296.

⁴⁹ *ibid* 35-37, 40, 294-295, 301.

been done in some American states). While municipal governments have pushed for greater taxing authority at times, and/or for a guaranteed share of federal and provincial taxes, provincial governments have tended to resist calls for a diversification of local revenue sources.

The high local reliance on property taxes has a profound effect on local politics and governance, since it pushes municipal authorities to aggressively pursue growth in the local property tax base, on which the fiscal health of the municipality depends. It likewise follows that the local fiscal capacity of municipalities is significantly influenced by the strength and health of their tax base. This situation tends to disadvantage rural municipalities, which (like their counterparts in other countries) experience lower rates of economic growth on average than large urban municipalities.⁵⁰

Local Government Spending

Municipalities have two budgets: operating budgets and capital budgets. Operating budgets cover the day-to-day expenses that are needed to deliver goods and services to residents and to ensure the internal municipal organization is running smoothly. Thus, the operating budget covers recurring costs, like salaries, office supplies, utilities, fuel, and contracted services. The capital budget covers large investments and infrastructure repairs, such as road renewal, sewer work, new buses, and new facilities. The most significant categories of public spending at the local level are roads and (in urban municipalities) public transit, water supply and sewage, and police and fire services. In Ontario, due to the provincial mandate that municipalities provide social services, there are significant municipal expenditures for health, social services, and housing.⁵¹

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Andrew C and Graham KA, *Canada in Cities: The Politics and Policy of Federal-Local Governance* (vol 7, McGill-Queen's Press 2014)

Sancton A, *Canadian Local Government: An Urban Perspective* (2nd edn, OUP 2015)

⁵⁰ For the implications of this rural/urban fiscal capacity divide in Ontario, see the First Entry to Report Section 2 (Local Finances) on Property Tax Reliance and the Re-Emergence of Provincial Funding Transfers to Local Government in Ontario.

⁵¹ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 293.

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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